

THE ROLE OF EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE COGNITIVE PROCESS OF CHILDREN

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Abstract: In this article, emotional development is understood as the formation of the child's emotional experience, which is the basis of the child's general intellectual development, on the basis of which, the organization of their chaotic ideas obtained as a result of interaction with the outside world, the development of observation, attention, thinking, imagination, children it is thought that it will be possible to learn and apply various methods of object inspection, to master sensory standards.

Key words: emotional experience, emotional norms, chaotic ideas, object, imagination, development, thinking, attention.

The younger the child, the more important the experience of emotional development in his cognitive development. In developing the emotional experience of a preschool child, the educator learns to use it as a means of emotional perception for a long time, and this process has its own stages: up to the standard (up to about 2 years) - the period of enriching the baby with impressions, preparing him for further assimilation. Sensor standards. At this stage, they create conditions for them to follow moving bright toys, hold objects of different shapes and textures. At the second stage, the child already collects certain reserve ideas about the various properties and characteristics of the objects of the surrounding world, and some of them begin to play the role of models that compare the properties of new objects. Children whose perception has some sensory information, they begin to generalize and systematize. At this stage, the assimilation of sensory standards such as color, shape, and size is available. The third stage lasts up to 5 years. At this stage, there is an introduction to generally accepted sensor standards and methods of their use. Along with the formation of the basic standards (color, shape, size), children learn methods of examining objects and other properties: weight, sense of touch, temperature indicators, and auditory reactions.

Perceived objects and events must be abstracted to reveal the connections with internal laws. And abstract thinking makes it possible to know the story in depth. Sensory knowledge creates an image of concrete things, but it cannot reveal the essence of events. So, in order to know the essence of events, it is necessary to find the generality that is characteristic of many things, not some things.

Thus, emotional development and abstract thinking are qualitatively different and at the same time interrelated stages of the entire cognitive process.

The formation of emotional experience in children at the preschool age is carried out not only by mastering emotional norms, but also by mastering the actions of perception, which are becoming more and more distinct and clear. Mastering the actions of object inspection by children is carried out as a specially organized perception of the object to determine the features that need to be known in order to successfully solve the future activity.

Depending on the goals, the same object is checked in different ways. The exam and the tested qualities themselves (N.A. Kurochkina, L.A. Paramonova, N.N. Poddyakov, E.S. Rogaleva, N.P. Sakulina). There is a general algorithm for many types of inspection: perception of the integral view of the object; mental division into main parts and determining their characteristics (shape, size, color, material); spatial correlation of parts with each other; selection of small details that establish their spatial location in relation to the main parts; repeated holistic perception of the subject (N.N. Podyakov). Examination according to this scheme helps children to master generalized methods of sensory knowledge that they can use in independent activities. Throughout preschool age, the nature of cognition changes: starting from manipulation with objects, the child gradually begins to get to know them based on sight, touch, as well as "visual palpation".

References:

1. D Yuldasheva, G Abdumuminova. Maktabgacha taʼlim yoshidagi bolalarda nutq madaniyatini shakllantirishda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanishning pedagogik asoslari. Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций 2 (3 Part 2), 8-11
- 2.Yuldasheva D.M. Pedagogical Features Of Mental Development Of Preschool Children. Solid State Technology.Volume: 63 Issue:6 Publication Year:2020. 14221-14225
- 3.Yuldasheva D.M. Anthropocentric Approach To Children's Speech Study. Section 2: Linguistic Theory, Applied Linguistics. Collection Of Materials Of The International Online Conference. www.research-support-center.com 2020.92-95
- 4.Yuldasheva D.M. The Methods Of Speech Development Of Preschool Children. Eurasian International Journal Of Multidisciplinary Research(Ijmr). Impact Factor: 7.6.11.November.
5. Юлдашева Д.М. Использование зоонимов в колыбельной песне-«алла», как аспект этнолингвистики. cyberleninka.ru

- 6.ДМ Юлдашева, Д Асқарова, М Зоҳидова. Ўзбек болалар нутқига доир матнларда лакуна. Academic research in educational sciences 2
- 7.D Yuldasheva. Anthropocentric approach to children's speech study. Конференции.
- 8.Y.D Maxamadaliyeva, M Matmusaeva. On Linguofolcloristic Units. International Journal of Culture and Modernity 11, 169-171

